

DYNAMIC FAILURE MONITORING OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES BY USING DEF EW FIBER-OPTIC STRAIN RATE SENSOR

K. Kageyama*, H. Murayama*, K. Uzawa, I. Ohsawa*, M. Kanai*, S. Akiyama*, S. Sugimoto** and S. Takeda**

*University of Tokyo, **JAXA

* 7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113-8656, Japan

e-mail: kageyama@giso.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp

SUMMARY

Some of authors have developed a new fiber-optic strain rate sensor, which is based on Doppler effect in flexible and expandable light-waveguide (DEF EW) [1]. Fiber-optic DEF EW sensor has extremely high resolution in the very wide frequency range from 10 Hz to 1 MHz. The DEF EW sensor has been applied to measurement of micro-failure process of composite materials. In the present paper, DEF EW sensor is applied to measurement of dynamic deformation and damage growth of composite laminate under impact loading. The experimental results show characteristic dynamic behavior of composite laminates.

Keywords: Impact, Damage, Fiber-optic sensor, Evaluation, Composite, Laminates

INTRODUCTION

Some of authors have developed a new fiber-optic strain rate sensor, which is based on Doppler effect in flexible and expandable light-waveguide (DEF EW) [1,2]. Fiber-optic DEF EW sensor has achieved extremely high resolution of nano-strain (10^{-10}) and has been applicable to the very wide frequency range from 10 Hz to 1 MHz. DEF EW sensor has been applied to AE monitoring of single fiber breakage [3], tensile failure of composite laminate [4], delamination [5] and damage of concrete structure [2], and it has also been applied to dynamic deformation monitoring of elastomer sheet [6]. Because of wide frequency range of DEF EW sensor, we can measure both dynamic deformation and elastic wave emission (AE waveform) in the frequency range from 1 Hz to 1 MHz by single DEF EW sensor output. In the present paper, DEF EW sensor is applied to measurement of dynamic deformation and damage monitoring of composite laminate under impact loading.

DOPPLER EFFECT IN FLEXIBLE AND EXPANDABLE LIGHT WAVE GUIDE (DEF EW)

Principle

Consider the light wave transmission in a media with refractive index, n . The light wave with frequency f_0 emitted from a moving point A (light source) is detected at other

moving point B (observer). The distance between points A and B changes from L to $L+dL$ during infinitesimal time interval dt . Doppler frequency shift f_D is observed at B by the observer,

$$f_D = -\frac{n}{\lambda_0} \cdot \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (1)$$

, where λ_0 is the light wavelength in a vacuum, and λ_0/n is the light wavelength in the media.

Fig. 1 Flexible and expandable light-waveguide

Fig. 2 Circular loop sensor

Next, consider an arbitrary light path (light-waveguide), Γ , as shown in Fig. 1. The path is flexible and expandable. It has finite overall length, L , and two ends, denoted as points A and B, respectively. An incident light from the one end A (light source) is transmitted through the waveguide and detected at the other end B (observer). When the waveguide moves or vibrates, the same equation as Eq. (1) is applicable,

$$f_D = -\frac{n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} \cdot \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (2)$$

, where n_{eq} is the equivalent refractive index of the waveguide and λ_0/n_{eq} is the equivalent length of light wave in the waveguide.

From a geometrical consideration (see detail in Appendix A), dL/dt is given by Eq. (3),

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = [\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{t}]_A^B + \int_{\Gamma} \kappa \cdot \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds \quad (3)$$

, where κ , \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{n} are the curvature, the velocity vector and the unit normal vector of the infinitesimal segment, ds , respectively, and \mathbf{t} is the unit direction vector defined at the end points A and B. (See Fig. 1.) The operation \cdot indicates inner product of two vectors.

From Eqs. (2) and (3), we obtain the following equation;

$$f_D = -\frac{n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} [\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{t}]_A^B - \frac{n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} \int_{\Gamma} \kappa \cdot \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds \quad (4)$$

This equation implies ‘‘Doppler effect in flexible and expandable light-waveguide’’. Displacement rate normal to the small segment of bent optical fiber effects on the frequency shift of light transmitted through the optical fiber and that the intensity of the frequency shift is proportional to the curvature of the bent fiber. We can detect the local displacement rate at the bent region in the optical fiber. As a feature of sensors, output

signal shall return to steady-state value when the external excitation is removed. It requests that the waveguide is elastic, or deformation is reversible.

Behavior of light wave traveling through the media is complex. Exact solution should be obtained by applying special theory of relativity, but the present result gives sufficient accuracy when motion of light-waveguide is much smaller than the light speed.

In the case of circular loop, sensitivity of displacement rate in the radial direction can be evaluated by integrating Eq. (4) on the displacement rate field. For simplicity, axisymmetrical deformation is assumed. Displacement rate, v_r , in the radial direction is uniform along the circular loop with radius of R . The theoretical frequency shift, f_D^{th} , is obtained.

$$f_D^{th} = -\frac{2\pi n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} v_r \quad (5)$$

In the case of N turns of loop, as shown in Fig. 2, the frequency shift becomes N times larger.

$$f_D^{th} = -\frac{2N\pi n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} v_r \quad (6)$$

By applying DEFEW sensor, we can evaluate dynamic displacement rate in the radial direction.

Measurement System

A Laser Doppler velocimeter (LDV) is used to detect the frequency shift. Detection electronics is FM discriminator. Light source is semiconductor laser (wavelength. λ_0 : 1550 nm), and heterodyne interference technique as shown in Fig. 3 is applied to the measurement in the present paper. An acousto-optical modulator (AOM) changes the frequency of the reference light source from f_0 to f_0+f_M ($f_M = 80$ MHz) in order to produce beating signals with frequency of f_D+f_M .

The sensitivity of the optical circular fiber sensor (average diameter: 20 mm, number of turn: 10) is calculated theoretically. By applying commercially available performance data of the LDV (Melectro, V1002) [7], the resolution and dynamic range are calculated. Extremely high resolution less than nano-strain (10^{-10}) is expected in the very wide frequency range from 1 kHz to 1 MHz [1]. total dynamic range reaches to 120-160 dB. Low frequency vibration of 1 Hz is detectable with sufficient sensitivity. The strain resolution of the newly developed sensor is extremely superior to the other fiber optic sensors, such as FBG. The developed fiber-optic sensor covers the measurement range from conventional strain gauge to AE sensor.

Fig. 3 Setup of measurement system

EXPERIMENTS

Figures 4 and 5 show the specimen and the fixture of impact test, respectively. Length, width and thickness of the specimen are 150 mm, 50 mm and 2.3 mm, respectively. Impact load was applied to the center of the specimen by a drop weight with the mass of 4.67 kg at three different energy levels. DEFEW sensors with diameter of 20 mm were bonded to both sides of the specimen. The specimens were made of prepreg sheets, Toray P2212-15 (carbon fiber Toray: T800H-12K-40B and matrix resin: Toray #3631), cured at 180°C with stacking sequence of laminate A $[0_2/45_2/-45_2/90_2]$ and laminate B $[45_2/0_2/-45_2/90_2]$.

Fig. 4 Specimen

Fig. 5 Test fixture

Impact damage monitoring system is schematically shown in Fig. 6. Time history of the impact force acting to the drop weight and the radial displacement rates detected by DEFEW sensors bonded on the front and back surfaces of specimen were measured and stored in the digital oscilloscope.

Fig. 6 Impact damage monitoring system

Ultrasonic C-scan image of damaged specimens were inspected by using ultrasonic flaw detector. Damaged area was determined by applying digital image process to the C-scan image data.

After the test, DEFEW sensors were removed and the specimens were cut and polished to observe the cross-sectional view of damages (delamination, matrix cracking, fiber breakage, etc) at the center of the specimen. Optical microscope was used to photographical observation.

OBSERVATION OF IMPACT DAMAGE

Ultrasonic C-scan image of the damaged specimen of laminate A after the impact test of the energy level of 1.5, 3.0 and 5.0 J are shown in Figs. 7 (a), (b) and (c), respectively. Relation between delamination area and impact energy is denoted in Fig. 8, which shows almost linear relations between them in both case of laminates A (o) and B (x).

(a) Energy level of 1.5 J (Laminate A)

(b) Energy level of 3.0 J (Laminate A)

(c) Energy level of 5.0 J (Laminate A)

Fig. 7 Ultrasonic C-scan image of the impact damaged specimens

Fig. 8 Relation between impact energy and delamination area

Cross-sectional view of laminates A and B are shown in Fig. 9. Progressive delamination growth and matrix cracking are observed in Laminate B. Laminate A shows more complex mechanism of damage growth than Laminate B.

(a) Laminate A, impact energy of 1.5 J

(d) Laminate B, impact energy of 1.5 J

(b) Laminate A, impact energy of 3.0 J

(e) Laminate B, impact energy of 3.0 J

(c) Laminate A, impact energy of 5.0 J

(f) Laminate B, impact energy of 5.0 J

Fig. 9 Cross-sectional view of impact damaged specimen

WAVE FORMS DETECTED BY DEFEW SENSOR

Figs.10 (a) - (c) show the velocity waves. The upper curves (red) show the velocity wave of the impact side sensor, and the lower curves (blue) show the one of the backside sensor. All velocity waves show macroscopic dynamic response upon which acoustic emission (AE) of impact damage is superimposed. The number of AE events increases in proportion to impact energy. At the lower energy level of 1.5 J impact, velocity waveforms detected at front and back surfaces are resemble each other, but result of higher energy level of 3.0 J impact shows different waveforms between front and back surfaces. It might the result of damage propagation through the thickness direction from front to back.

(a) Impact energy level of 1.5 J

(b) Impact energy level of 3.0 J

(c) Impact energy level of 5.0 J

Fig. 10 Velocity waveform of the impact test of Laminate B

Time integration is applied to velocity waveform as shown in Fig. 10, and the displacement versus time diagrams are obtained in the present study. Figs. 11 (a)-(c) show the results of time integration of impact test of Laminate B. In each figure, the upper (blue) and lower (red) curves show deformation of back and front surface, respectively. The front surface shows larger deformation than back surface because of dent at impact point. Combination of velocity and displacement versus time diagram indicates useful chart for damage and condition monitoring. An example is shown in Fig. 12.

Velocity and displacement versus time diagram can be divided into 4 sections as shown in Fig. 12. Section 1 indicates elastic response of the specimen in an undamaged state. Impact load increases to the maximum level in Section 2, and elastic wave emissions due to damage growth are observed at frequent intervals in Section 2. Section 3 is unloading process and no remarkable damage occurs. Specimen vibrates freely with the characteristic frequency in Section 4 after impact force was removed.

(a) Impact energy level of 1.5 J

(b) Impact energy level of 3.0 J

(c) Impact energy level of 5.0 J

Fig. 11 Displacement versus time diagram of Laminate B

Fig. 12 Combination of velocity and displacement versus time diagram

Free vibration was observed in Fig. 10 after impact force was removed. The characteristic frequencies of the specimens after impact damage are listed in Table 1. The characteristic frequency decreases as impact energy increases. Change of the characteristic frequency might relate to impact damage area.

Table 1 Characteristic frequency of the specimens after impact damage

Impact energy	Laminate A	Laminate B
1.5 J	11.6 kHz	11.5 kHz
3.0 J	9.2 kHz	9.2 kHz
5.0 J	7.0 kHz	7.9 kHz

CONCLUSIONS

DEFEW sensor shows excellent performance to simultaneous dynamic monitoring of deformation and damage of composite material under impact loading. DEF EW sensor has sufficient resolution and frequency range to the drop-weight impact test. The results of detected waveforms give new insight of mechanism of impact damage of composite materials.

References

- [1] K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, K. Uzawa, I. Ohsawa, M. Kanai, Y. Akematsu, K. Nagata, and T. Ogawa, "Doppler Effect in Flexible and Expandable Light Waveguide and Development of New Fiber-Optic Vibration/Acoustic Sensor". JOURNAL OF LOGHTWAVE TECHNOLOGY, VOL.24, NO.4, APRIL 2006.
- [2] K. Kageyama, et al., "Acoustic Emission Monitoring of a Reinforced Concrete Structure by Applying New Fiber-Optic Sensors", Smart Materials and Structures, Vol. 14, P. S52, 2005.
- [3] K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, K. Uzawa, I. Ohsawa, M. Kanai, Y. Akematsu and T. Matsuo, "Measurement of failure process of single filament embedded in resin matrix by using a fiber-optic strain rate sensor", Proc. ICCM-15, Durban (2005).
- [4] K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, I. Ohsawa, K. Uzawa, M. Kanai and Y. Akematsu, "Measurement of Failure Process in Carbon /Epoxy Laminates by Using Fiber-Optic Strain Rate Sensor", Proceedings of 15th International Conference on Composite Materials(CD-ROM), June, 2005, Durban.
- [5] K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, S. Atsuta, I. Ohsawa, M. Kanai, "Elastic Wave Emission during Delamination Growth of Carbon/Epoxy Monitored with Fiber-Optic DEF EW Strain Rate Sensor", 16th International Conference on Composite Materials, pp. 54-55, 2007/07.
- [6] K. Uzawa, K. Kageyama, H. Murayama, I. Ohsawa and M. Kanai, "Deformation Monitoring of an Elastomer Using Fiber-Optic Strain Rate Sensor", Proceedings of 15th International Conference on Composite Materials(CD-ROM), June, 2005, Durban
- [7] Technical Report of "VIBRODUCER V1002", Denshigiken Co. Ltd., 2002.